

A Prospective Study of Audiological Outcomes after Underlay Tympanoplasty in Chronic Otitis Media

Shweta Anand¹, Mahesh Virupakshi Kattimani², Preeti³

¹Associate Professor, Dept of ENT, PMCH, Udaipur, Rajasthan

²Associate Professor, Dept of ENT, PMCH, Udaipur, Rajasthan

³3rd Year Resident, Dept of ENT, PMCH, Udaipur, Rajasthan

Received: 21-06-2024 / Revised: 04-07-2024 / Accepted: 20-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mahesh Virupakshi Kattimani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic otitis media is a common condition seen in patients attending the otolaryngology clinic and is an important public health problem. It is a chronic inflammatory disease of the middle ear causing conductive hearing loss that can range in severity up to 60dB. Pure tone audiometry is used to determine the degree, type and the configuration of hearing loss and to know a person's hearing threshold to provide a basis for diagnosis and management.

Aim: To study the audiological outcome after underlay tympanoplasty in mucosal type of chronic otitis media.

Material & Methods: A prospective observational study was carried out in ENT department of PMCH, Udaipur from December 2022 to May 2024. Informed written consent was taken from all the patients. Seventy patients of chronic otitis media were selected as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. Thorough history and clinical examination of ear, nose and throat was done. Preoperative hearing level was evaluated by pure tone audiometry. Underlay Type-I Tympanoplasty was done under local/ general anaesthesia by post-aural approach using temporalis fascia as graft material. Patients were followed up after 3 months for graft uptake and hearing assessment.

Results: In our study majority of patients were in the age group of 21-30 years. 27 patients are male and 43 are females. Most common presenting complaints was otorrhea (100%), followed by hearing loss (97%), earache (37%), vertigo (2.9%) and tinnitus (7.4%). Majority of patients had mild conductive hearing loss 26-40dB loss in 36 patients (51.4%), followed by moderate hearing loss 41-54 dB loss in 32 patients (45.71%). After underlay tympanoplasty 54 patients (77.14%) came under normal hearing range followed by 26-40 dB loss in 16 patients (22.8%). Graft uptake was seen in 68 patients (97.14%).

Conclusion: It can be concluded from our study that there is significant hearing improvement in patients who underwent underlay tympanoplasty as there is gain in hearing threshold after 3 months follow-up.

Keywords: Chronic Otitis Media, Hearing Threshold, Temporalis Fascia Graft, Underlay Tympanoplasty.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Chronic otitis media implies a permanent abnormality of the pars tensa or flaccida, most likely a result of earlier acute otitis media, negative middle ear pressure or otitis media with effusion.[1]

It is a common condition seen in patients attending the otolaryngology clinic and is an important public health problem with substantial economic and societal costs, affecting 0.5%- 30% of community. It is a major cause of acquired hearing impairment especially in the developing world.[2]

A conservative estimate of no. of people in the world suffering from chronic otitis media is over 20 million. (3) As per WHO, the prevalence of chronic otitis media in Indian population is approximately 2% which is comparatively higher than found in

developed countries like that of USA and UK where the prevalence is <1%.[3]

As per the American Academy of Ophthalmology and Otolaryngology, tympanoplasty is defined as a procedure to eradicate disease in the middle ear and to reconstruct the hearing mechanism, with or without tympanic membrane grafting.[4]

Myringoplasty is defined as an operation in which the reconstructive procedure is limited to repair of a tympanic membrane perforation.[5] Different graft material have been used such as perichondrium, cartilage, periosteum, fat, subcutaneous tissue, amniotic membrane, dermal matrix and fibroblasts to construct the tympanic membrane, the most accepted of which is temporalis fascia autograft and al-

most always the most favourable graft for its immunological compatibility.[6] Tympanoplasty can be done by two techniques-overlay and underlay technique.[7] In overlay technique the graft is kept over the remnant of the tympanic membrane after removing the epithelial layer of the tympanic membrane. This technique is difficult to perform hence not very popular. Epithelial pearl formation, blunting of anterior sulcus and lateralization of graft are the common complications of this technique. In underlay tympanoplasty the graft is kept under the remnant of tympanic membrane. This technique is very easy to learn and to adapt, hence very popular. The medialization of graft especially anteriorly is the commonest complication of this technique.[6] Tympanoplasty can be done by three approaches namely postaural, endaural and trans-canal. Post aural approach is commonly used. Hearing loss can be assessed by tuning fork test and pure tone audiometry. Pure tone audiometry is used to determine the degree, type and the configuration of hearing loss. This study is done to determine the audiological outcome after underlay tympanoplasty by comparing hearing threshold of patient preoperative and postoperative.

Materials and Method

This study is a prospective observational study which was carried out in ENT department of PMCH, Udaipur from December 2022 to May 2024. Informed written consent was taken from all the patients.

Seventy patients who presented with signs and symptoms of mucosal type of chronic otitis media

were included in this study. Thorough history and clinical examination of ear, nose and throat was done. Pre operative hearing level was evaluated by tuning fork tests and pure tone audiometry. Pre-anesthetic check-up was done. Underlay Type-I Tympanoplasty was done under local/ general anesthesia by postaural approach using temporalis fascia as graft material. Antibiotics and antihistaminics were given post-operatively. Stitches were removed on 7th postoperative day. Patients were followed up after 3 months for graft uptake and hearing assessment by pure tone audiometry.

Selection Criteria for the Participants

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who are of 11-60 years of age.
- Patients of mucosal type of chronic otitis media with pure conductive hearing loss.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who are below 11 year and above 60 years of age
- Patients with SNHL or mixed hearing loss, malignancy, otitis externa and any complication of chronic otitis media will be excluded for the surgery.
- Patients who do not turn up for post operative audiological evaluation in due course of time
- Patient of squamous type of chronic otitis media.
- Patients who are undergoing revision surgery.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to the age

S.no.	Age group(years)	No. of cases	Percentage
I	11-20	7	10
II	21-30	21	30
III	31-40	14	20
IV	41-50	12	17.14
V	51-60	3	4.28
VI	61-70	5	7.14
Total		70	100

Figure 1:

In our study majority of patients were in the age group of 21-30 years (mean age of 24.5 years) followed by 31-40 then 41-50 then 11-20 then 60-70 and lastly 50-70.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to Gender

Gender	No. of patients	%
Male	27	38.5
Female	43	68.42
Total	70	100

Figure 2:

In our study, out of 70 patients 27 were males and 43 were females.

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to Symptoms

S.no.	Symptoms	No. of patients	Percentage
I	Otorrhea	70	100
II	Hearing loss	68	97.14
III	Earache	23	37.14
IV	Vertigo	2	2.9
V	Tinnitus	5	7.14
VI	Total	70	100

Figure 3:

In our study, most common presenting complaints was otorrhea (100%), followed by hearing loss(97%), earache (37%) , vertigo (2.9%) and tinnitus (7.4%).

Table 4: Distribution of patients according to Pre-operative hearing loss

Average Air conduction threshold (in dBs.) between	No. of pts	Percentage
26.1- 30	10	14.28
30.1-35	12	17.14
35.1-40	14	20
40.1-45	16	22.85
45.1-50	14	20
>50	2	4.28
Total	70	100

Figure 4:

Majority of patients were under mild conductive hearing loss 26-40dB loss in 36 patients (51.4%), followed by moderate hearing loss 41-54 dB loss in 32 patients (45.71%).

Table 5: Distribution of patients according to Post-operative hearing gain

Hearing gain in dB	No. of pts.	Percentage
1-10	13	18.57
10.1-15	11	15.71
15.1-20	10	14.28
20.1-25	20	28.57
25.1-30	9	12.85
30.1-35	7	10
Total	70	100

Figure 5:

Post management 54 patients (77.14%) came under normal hearing range followed by 26-40 dB loss in 16 patients (22.8).

Table 6: Distribution of patients according to Graft uptake

Graft Status	No. of patients	Percentage
Graft uptake	68	97.14
Graft failure	2	2.8
Total	70	100

Figure 6:

Graft uptake was seen in 68 patients (97.14%) out of 70.

Discussion

In present study commonest age group affected was 21-30 years (30%) followed by 31-40 years (20%). The youngest case was of 11 years and oldest case was of 61 year old. These are more or less comparable to other studies done in past. It is more common during this age due to ecological and environment factors. It is also common due to presence of sinusitis and DNS in this age group. In present study males 38.5% and females 68.5%. This could be due to lack of health awareness, poor socioeconomic status and poor hygiene in females. In our study all 70 patients presented with otorrhea (100%), 68 patients with hearing loss (97.14%), 26 with earache (37.14%), 5 with headache (7.19%). These findings are similar to previous study done by S Varshnay et al in 2010. They observed that ear discharge seen in 100% of cases, followed by hearing loss in 88.67% of cases. [8]

Nishant Kumar et al in 2011 observed otorrhoea was the commonest complaint in 52 patients (81.25%) followed by hearing impairment in 40 (62.50%), itching in the ear in 6 (9.37%), tinnitus in 12 (18.75%) and pain in 2 cases (3.12%). [9]

S. Shetty in 2011 observed that out of 50 patients, 47 patients (94%) showed excellent surgical success rate by means of graft uptake and only 3 patients had residual perforations of the tympanic membrane. [3] These findings are similar to the findings in our study in which 68 out of 70 patients had healthy graft uptake and only 2 patients had graft failure.

We observed that before surgical management majority of patients were under mild conductive hearing loss 26-40dB loss in 36 patients (51.4%), followed by moderate hearing loss 41-54 dB loss in 32 patients (45.71%). Whereas post management 54 patients (77.14%) came under normal hearing range followed by 26-40 dB loss in 16 patients (22.8%).

In the study done by S. Shetty in 2011 majority of patients were with mild to moderate hearing loss that ranged from 35.1–50 dB i.e., 41 patients out of 50 (82.00%) and post operative majority of patients have been benefited by gaining 15.1–30 dB of hearing i.e., 38 out of 50 (76%). [3]

Maharjan M et al (2009) observed hearing status of all 119 perforated tympanic membrane is mild loss 29 (24.37%), moderate loss 63 (52.94%), moderate severe loss 24 (20.17%) and severe loss 3 (2.52%), which is similar to our study. [10]

Thus, Underlay Tympanoplasty plays an important role in improving hearing status of patients with mucosal type of chronic otitis media.

Conclusion

Chronic otitis media is very common disease in the practice of otorhinolaryngology. Otorrhoea and hearing loss are the common presenting symptoms. Otoscopy, examination of ear under microscope, tuning fork test and pure tone audiometry play an important role in correct diagnosis of chronic otitis media. Underlay tympanoplasty using temporalis fascia graft is a safe and effective procedure in im-

proving the quality of life of patients by eradicating the disease and making the ear dry with improvement in hearing. Success rate of graft uptake depends on surgeon's technical skills, biological and pathological factors of patients. It can be concluded from our study that there is significant hearing improvement in patients who underwent underlay tympanoplasty as there is gain in hearing threshold after 3 months follow-up.

References

1. Scott-Brown's diseases of the ear, nose and throat, 4th Edition, 4 Volumes Edited by John Ballantyne and John Groves, 2,816 pp, illus, Butterworth's, Woburn, MA, 1979.
2. Shetty S. Pre-Operative and Post-Operative Assessment of Hearing following Tympanoplasty. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2012 Dec; 64(4):377-81.
3. Muqtadir F, S. R. A study of clinical profile of patients with CSOM attending tertiary care hospital. International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery. 2017 Dec 22;4.
4. Atal A, Goyal A, Solanki B. Hearing outcome following myringoplasty for CSOM: a study of 60 patients. Galore International Journal of Health Sciences & Research. 2019; 4(1): 9-11.
5. Jyoti D, Saraf A, Arti. Assessment of hearing following tympanoplasty-A Hospital Based study. International Journal of Innovative Research in Medical Science.2019 July 07;4.
6. Sheehy JL, Anderson RG Myringoplasty: a review of 472 cases. Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol 1980; 89:331-334
7. Gupta S, Kalsotra P. Hearing gain in different types of tympanoplasties. Indian J Otol 2013; 19:186-93.
8. Varshney S, Nangia A, Bist SS, Singh RK, Gupta N, Bhagat S. Ossicular Chain Status in Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media in Adults. Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery. 2010 Oct;62(4):421-6.
9. K Nishant, Chilke D, Puttewar M.P.- Clinical Profile of Tubotympanic CSOM and its management with special reference to site and size of tympanic membrane perforation, Eustachian tube function and three flap tympanoplasty. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2012 Mar;64(1):5-12.
10. Maharjan M, Kafle P, Bista M, Shrestha S, Toran K. Observation of hearing loss in patients with chronic suppurative otitis media tubotympanic type. Kathmandu University Medical Journal. 1970 Jan 1;7(4):397-401.